

GINNGER

**CO-DESIGNING
NEIGHBOURHOOD
REGENERATION**

Co-funded by the
European Union

Towards a participatory urban development

A **greener future** for Europe begins right at our doorsteps and demands **active citizen participation**.

GINNIGER engages communities in implementing **sustainable regeneration plans** for their neighbourhoods.

To achieve this, we combine an innovative **co-creation methodology** with **digital solutions** to ensure all voices are heard while enhancing energy efficiency, implementing green mobility and promoting a sustainable use of resources.

1

co-creation
methodology

6

pilot
cities

13

digital
solutions

21

regeneration
actions

950+

inhabitants
involved

The objectives we aim to achieve

PLACE-BASED APPROACH

Implement tailored actions for sustainable neighbourhoods

CO-CREATION METHODOLOGY

Analyse conditions for co-creation in urban transformation

CONTEXT ANALYSIS

Develop methods for participatory neighbourhood regeneration

DIGITAL TOOLKIT

Utilise digital solutions for decision-making and implementation

ON-SITE VALIDATION

Test and validate GINGER solutions in six pilot cities

REPLICABILITY STRATEGY

Ensure replicability of proposed solutions

Engaging communities in 6 pilot cities

The aspects we improve through our digital solutions

ENERGY

RENOVATION

RESOURCES

MOBILITY

PARIS

Empowering communities
for energy efficiency,
resilience and accessibility

LANGREO

Implementing sustainable
solutions to tackle energy
poverty

MURCIA

Advancing energy
communities and
sustainable mobility

Our approach enables people across Europe to co-create more **affordable, sustainable and inclusive neighbourhoods**.

We believe that understanding the community's needs is key to addressing them. That's why the initiatives GINGER promotes are tailored to the **unique history, culture and socio-economic conditions** of each pilot.

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